

MOBILE ANAESTHETIC PRACTICE –A NIGERIAN (10 YEARS) EXPERIENCE IN NIGER-DELTA

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ABSTRACT

The surgical needs of our environment have necessitated an increased demand for quality/improved anaesthetic care; where local anaesthetic techniques would not suffice. Also increased awareness amongst the populace has brought about this need. The need to improve the indices of maternal and child morbidity and mortality which in international circles are presently yardsticks of measuring development among developing nations has acted as the catalyst for ensuring safety amongst these very vulnerable class of persons. With these factors in view especially with the availability of scarce anaesthetic manpower and resources, government and private individual and even NGOs are asking for improved anaesthetic services. My experience of mobile anaesthetic service provision over the past ten years as an anaesthetist is my little way of bringing health care to the doorstep of the people in south-south Nigeria. The procedures undertaken were mainly obstetric, gynecological, general surgical, minor neurosurgical, urology and minor thoracic surgeries. The techniques adopted were regional and general anaesthesia using a portable Boyle's machine and accessories. Recommendations derived from this experience are as follows 1)hospitals work within the limitation of manpower resources .2)Availability of anaesthetic register and contact maintained especially in emergencies .3)Referral systems be made use of .4)With the availability of mobile complete anaesthetic unit purchase of anaesthetic machines may be unnecessary in small hospitals as they often go bad from disuse.5)More health workers need training in basic life support, advanced cardiac life support, advanced trauma life support and acute life threatening events recognition and treatment (ALERT) courses. These should be incorporated into medical curriculum.

KEYWORDS: Mobile Anaesthesia, Safety, Manpower limitations, breaking barriers, Training.

INTRODUCTION

Surgical intervention may become necessary for patients in rural, suburban and urban hospitals where the doctors are skilled and trained to do so. To facilitate this, some form of anaesthesia may be necessary requiring the presence of an anaesthetist. The paucity of such anaesthetic services was the motivating factor in the provision of mobile anaesthetic service-taking anaesthesia to the people: exploring the possibility of improving surgical safety profile. My short experience spans ten years of taking anaesthesia where it is needed and when it is needed. In the short period of time, procedures were undertaken in a wide range of surgical specialties which in most cases needed special anaesthetic care mostly in unconventional and challenging circumstances in private hospitals and government institutions. The availability of such mobile services removes the severe restrictions imposed on the surgeon by the use of agents like ketamine which is commonly used for minor surgeries; especially in the rural and sub-urban areas. In essence we provided anaesthesia without barriers.

DISCUSSION

In view of the shortage of anaesthetic manpower, mobile anaesthetic practice becomes a pattern of practice which the qualified anaesthetist adopts. This pattern of practice is further enhanced by the seeming low

anaesthetist /surgeon ratio; a trend which is more pronounced in the tropics (Soyanwo *et al.*, (1999) . Most anaesthetics are provided by non-physicians, sometimes under the direct supervision of the surgeon. With increasing levels of enlightenment, patients' demands pressure the average surgeon in his private practice. This increasing trend equates to an increased request for anaesthetic cover by private hospitals. Anaesthesia is known to impact significantly on maternal and child health indices. These indices are tools of measuring development especially in developing countries where basic standards of living and health care determine life expectancy (Pitterson 2010). A significant percentage of women die at childbirth and pregnancy related circumstances. In Africa 1 in 31 women die from causes related to childbirth while in the developed countries the figure is 1 in 4300 (Lanre-Abbas 2008). These figures are becoming internationally unacceptable; and safe anaesthesia goes a long way in preventing these unnecessary deaths. More so surgery has become accepted as a critical component of public health in developing countries (Farmer *et al* 2008). By extension anaesthesia for these patients becomes a critical component factor that affects outcome and health indices. The areas covered in this experience were mainly in Edo, Delta, Ondo, Rivers and Bayelsa states, south-south Nigeria.

Though the subject of anaesthesia is part of the curriculum of the medical school, the exposure to the subject is so short that the doctor requires some form of further training (postgraduate) to cope with patient needs thereby ensuring safety. Though these services are available in teaching hospitals, there is an acute shortage in general hospitals. This acute shortage necessitated the training of nurse anaesthetists in some institutions; and the commencement of the one-year postgraduate diploma programme in anaesthesia by the West African college of Surgeons. Even this level of training is inadequate to care for some of these patients needing surgical care. The four to six years' fellowship programme in anaesthesia and intensive care presently undertaken by the West African postgraduate medical college and national postgraduate medical college are meant to care for these categories of individuals.

The factors that make mobile anaesthesia necessary in our environment are

1. Patients desire to have surgery in facilities that do not have anaesthetists
2. In surgical outreaches where care is taken to the people who cannot afford care in government or private hospitals
3. In some hospitals with nurse anaesthetists where specialist skills are required especially in previous critical incidents
4. Patient transport especially in the critically ill and sometimes in altitudes (i.e. aero planes).

Mobile anaesthesia is given in private and public hospital depending on the arrangement. The type of anaesthetic administered depends not only on patient and surgery, but also on the environment and conditions. In spite of these variables, the team is equipped to cope in adverse unconventional conditions going by acceptable minimum standards. For the purpose of this discourse I would categorize these institutions into, private hospitals, Industrial clinics/hospitals, surgical outreach programs, and government general hospitals.

Private hospitals.

The high levels of enlightenment and desire to give good quality care makes private hospital request for the anaesthetic coverage. We have noted with interest that quite a number of private hospitals claim to have anaesthetic machines. On inspection of some those machines we found them to be rusty and unsafe for use on patients. This was mainly due to disuse in such outfits where regional anaesthesia and intravenous ketamine was predominantly adopted and sometimes improperly administered (Kolawole 2001). Our mobile anaesthetic unit was useful in these circumstances where the patients needed balanced anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation. In these instances, we have advised these doctors to avail themselves of services provided by our mobile unit. An increasing number of surgical procedures are done in private hospitals as the patronage of these outfits is on

the increase especially when they render skilled services that are not available in government outfits (Okohue *et al.*, 2009) . This makes the provision of safe anaesthesia desirable.

Scope

Paediatric Anaesthesia

Cleft lip/ palate repairs, adenotonsillectomy, intussusceptions, Airway foreign body removal, Herniotomy, Umbilical herniorrhaphy, Circumcision, Burns

Obstetrics/Gynaecology

Caesarean section, Postpartum haemorrhage, Myomectomy, Total abdominal hysterectomy, vaginal hysterectomies, Ruptured ectopic pregnancy, ovarian torsion

General surgery: Appendicectomy, Intestinal obstruction, Bowel resection /anastomosis, Triple by-pass, Thyroidectomy and Perforated Typhoid

Trauma/Orthopedics

Fractured femur/tibia, fractured humerus, Sequestrectomy, Osteotomy

Hip replacement, Knee surgery

Maxillofacial

Maxillary/mandibular fractures, Jaw tumours, Cleft lips/palate repairs

Cardiothoracic

Oesophageal surgeries, Vascular (peripheral stab wound). Chest tube insertion

Urology

Prostatectomy (including TURP), Nephrectomy

Neurosurgery

V-p shunt, craniotomy (selected), bore hole

Industrial clinics / hospitals.

These clinics have gradually evolved into hospitals where high levels of care are given to staff. Some are so well equipped and even better equipped than some government hospitals. They adopt international safety standards even in the care of surgical patients and therefore seek the best of professional services available in the environment. Their zero tolerance for morbidity and mortality drives the need for equipment and high standards of care. For these centres the initial approach is provision of anaesthetic services, which gradually evolves into the setting up of an in-house anaesthetic service by the employment of the requisite staff. Periodic training of these staff is an integral part of the arrangement; training in basic life support and advanced cardiac life support being inclusive. This knowledge is useful in the event of resuscitation before the arrival of the anaesthetic team.

Scope

Paediatric Anaesthesia

Cleft lip/ palate repairs, Adenotonsillectomy, Intussusceptions, Airway foreign body removal, herniotomy, Umbilical herniorrhaphy, Circumcision, Burns

Obstetrics/Gynaecology

Caesarean section, Postpartum haemorrhage, Myomectomy, Total abdominal hysterectomy, vaginal hysterectomies, Ruptured ectopic pregnancy, ovarian torsion

General surgery: Appendicectomy, Intestinal obstruction, Bowel resection /anastomosis, Triple by-pass, Thyroidectomy and Perforated Typhoid

Trauma/orthopedics

Fractured femur/tibia, Fractured humerus, Sequestrectomy, Osteotomy, Hip replacement, Knee surgery

Maxillofacial

Maxillary and mandibular fractures, Jaw tumours, Cleft lips/palate repairs

Cardiothoracic

Oesophageal surgeries, Vascular (peripheral stab wound). Chest tube insertion

Urology

Prostatectomy (including TURP), Nephrectomy

Neurosurgery

V-p shunt, craniotomy (selected), bore hole

Surgical outreach programmes.

Surgical outreaches are done mostly by NGOs, taking Medicare to the remote areas of Nigeria and the Niger-Delta. In these places regional and local anaesthesia are preferred; but when it becomes necessary general anaesthesia is adopted. In these cases, patient selection is the key. Attempts are made at bloodless surgeries as blood transfusion can be a challenge in some of these patients.

Scope

Paediatric Anaesthesia

Cleft lip/ palate repairs, Intussusceptions, Herniotomy, Umbilical herniorrhaphy

Circumcision, Burns

General surgery

Appendicectomy, Intestinal obstruction, Bowel resection/anastomosis

Thyroidectomy

General hospitals/Federal medical centres;

The need for skilled manpower at the level of consultant anaesthetist necessitates this especially in acutely life-threatening circumstances.

Scope

Paediatric Anaesthesia

Cleft lip/ palate repairs, Adenotonsillectomy, Intussusceptions, Airway foreign body removal, Herniotomy, Umbilical herniorrhaphy, Circumcision, Burns

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Tools

The tools available are the following and efforts are made to upgrade equipments in view of evolving challenges

Mobile Anaesthetic Boyle's machine (picture 1)

Breathing systems- Bain circuit

Endotracheal tubes (sizes 2.0-8.5mm)

Laryngeal mask airways (sizes 2-4)

Oropharyngeal/nasopharyngeal airways (sizes 000-5)

Laryngoscopes (conventional and MCoy)

Spinal needles (sizes 22, 25, 26, 27)

Epidural packs/sets with catheters

Monitors -Noninvasive blood pressure monitor (NIBP)

-Pulse oximetry (SpO₂)

Continuous electrocardiogram (ECG)

Stethoscope (sometimes adapted as precordial stethoscope)

Transport ventilators

Automated electrical defibrillators

Drugs- Compliment f anaesthetic medications

Transport vehicle/ambulance

Personnel

These surgeries were undertaken most times by a Consultant Anaesthetist and sometimes with the assistance of an Anaesthetic technician. It is not unusual to mobilize some operating theatre staff whenever the need arose, especially at endotracheal intubation.

Logistics

Though these surgeries were either electives or emergencies our response was made easy by the availability a personal vehicle for movement to venues of surgeries sometimes with the assistance of a driver. For elective cases patients are usually reviewed the preceding day while surgeries are fixed mostly between 5:30 am and 8am. For long duration surgeries especially maxillofacial procedures were done mostly at night, extending sometimes into the early hours of the morning. In emergencies, reviews are done in the immediate preoperative period. Patient resuscitation goes on concomitantly. The advent of global system of mobile communication makes for easy communication and response to emergencies and even aid preoperative preparation before we get to the site of surgery, assembly of materials, staff and scheduling of electives. These surgeries were done in metropolitan and rural settings. Where necessary patients are transferred to places where safe anaesthesia and surgery could be administered.

Minimal conditions for optimum care in the Operating Theatre

Lighting, electrical wall fittings cooling (where available), operating table and a table to place the anaesthetic machine were basic requirements in the operating theatre. In situations of power outage, electrical generating sets came in handy. Phones, torches and laryngoscope lights were alternatives that could be useful in emergencies, though for much shorter periods of time. Manual suction were an essential part of our kits.

Ethics:

Sometimes we are confronted with ethical issues. Where no surgery is necessary the maxim "above all, do no harm" guides our practice (<http://www.mdcnigeria.org>). Sometime despite patients' inability to pay we ensure prompt resuscitation and embark on the surgery. When necessary patients are referred to bigger hospitals where they can get better care accompanying them sometimes on life support on transport ventilator. Though most times the transport is by road, we have had occasions to transport some patients by boat or by flight.

CONCLUSION

Recommendations derived from this experience are as follows 1)hospitals work within the limitation of manpower resources 2)availability of anaesthetic register and contact maintained especially in emergencies 3)referral systems be made use of 4)with the availability of mobile complete anaesthetic unit purchase of anaesthetic machines may be unnecessary in small hospitals as they often go bad from disuse.5)more health workers need training in basic life support, advanced cardiac life support and advanced trauma life support and acute life threatening events recognition and treatment (ALERT) courses. This should be incorporated into medical curriculum.

Abbreviations

NGO- Non –governmental organisation
BLS=Basic Life Support
ACLS- Advanced Cardiac Life Support
ALERT- Acute Life-threatening events recognition and treatment
TURP- Transurethral resection of the prostate
V-P Shunt- Ventriculo-peritoneal shunt

Competing interests

The author states that there are no competing interests

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7